

IRradiation Effects on HTS for Fusion
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Book of Abstracts

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Scope:

The goal of the workshop is to create a strong network of researchers that unites the competences coming from the nuclear fusion community with those from scholars who worked on the high temperature superconductors (HTS). In our view this is a crucial step to tackle the several challenges related to the effects of particle radiation on the HTS tapes that are enabling the development of compact fusion reactors.

Topics:

- HTS technology for fusion
 - State-of-the-art of HTS wires and tapes
 - Needs for magnets in compact fusion reactors
- Radiation damage
 - Neutronics and radiation environment
 - Shielding materials and designs
 - Modelling radiation damage in HTS
 - Irradiation experiments on HTS
 - Irradiation of HTS for pinning optimization
 - Advanced methods and facilities

The workshop is organized in the framework of the bilateral project "SUPERNEON - Study of high-temperature SUPERconductors NEutron radiation damage for compact fusiON reactors" between Politecnico di Torino and MIT, funded by MAECI.

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website: <https://www.superfusion.org/iref25/>
contact: iref@polito.it

ENEA activities on HTS conductors for fusion magnet applications

G. Celentano^{1,*}, M. Bombardieri¹, S. Chiarelli¹, V. Corato¹, G. De Marzi¹, A. Di Zenobio¹, R. Freda¹, M. Marchetti¹, A. Masi¹, L. Muzzi¹, S. Turtù¹, A. Rufoloni¹, A. Vannozzi¹, M. Caponero², A. Polimadei², A. Anemona³, A. della Corte³, A. Formichetti³, A. Bragagni⁴, M. Seri⁴, R. Bonifetto⁵, A. Zappatore⁵, M. Breschi⁶, G. Colombo⁶, A. Trotta⁷, F. Zanon⁷

¹ Superconductivity Laboratory, Nuclear Department, ENEA, Frascati, Italy

² Fiber Optic Sensors Laboratory, Nuclear Department, ENEA, Frascati, Italy

³ ICAS S.r.l., Frascati, Italy

⁴ Tratos Cavi S.p.A, Pieve S. Stefano, Italy

⁵ NEMO Group, Politecnico di Torino, Italy

⁶ Bologna University, Department of Electrical, Electronic and Information Engineering, Bologna, Italy

⁷ Eni S.p.A, Marghera, Italy

* Contact: giuseppe.celentano@enea.it

The emergence of High Temperature Superconductors (HTS) technology, based on Rare-Earth-Barium-Copper Oxide (REBCO) tapes, named coated conductors, is playing a revolutionary role in the fusion sector. This is due to the great potential of HTS to generate higher magnetic fields and operate with higher temperature margins, which can extend the design limits imposed by the Low Temperature Superconductor (LTS) Nb-based coil technology and promote alternative approaches based on a more compact reactor design [1]. A measure of the enthusiasm is provided by the rise of the private fusion industry in recent years, with a huge number of private-financed start-up companies considering HTS as the key technology to achieve the goal of making net energy from fusion a more affordable reality [2]. With this perspective, in the last decade, great efforts were dedicated to developing HTS-based conductors for fusion magnets. Based on its strong expertise and skills in LTS conductors and HTS materials, the ENEA Superconductivity Laboratory pushed further the R&D activity on HTS fusion conductors, initially conceiving, together with its industrial partner ICAS, the aluminum slotted-core concept, characterized by stacks of HTS tapes incorporated into slots created in an extruded Al stabilizer [3]. More recently, an experimental campaign funded by EUROfusion to investigate thermal stability and quench phenomena on slotted-core cables was carried out at the SULTAN facility. Sub-size samples were tested with forced-flow supercritical He under a maximum background magnetic field of 11 T. Samples showed good thermal stability and strong tolerance to successive quenches, with minimal performance degradation only after reaching a hotspot temperature of more than 200 K. In the framework of the EUROfusion work program for DEMO, ENEA has recently developed a new HTS conductor for the hybrid Central Solenoid (CS) coil system, operating at 18 T, 4.2 K with a rated current of 60 kA. With this aim, the SECTOR ASsembled (SECAS) cable was conceived, equipped with BRAided Stacks of Tapes (BRAST) placed in the slots manufactured in a set of copper stabilizing sectors [4]. In view of the final qualification of the cable performances to be carried out at the SULTAN facility, several sub-size prototypes have been manufactured and tested at the liquid nitrogen temperature, to investigate the BRAST tolerance to and feasibility of the manufacturing steps for the final conductor assembly. Since quench detection on HTS coils represents a crucial issue, due to the challenges of conventional voltage-based systems, ENEA has recently started, in the framework of the collaboration with ENI, a dedicated R&D activity aimed at exploiting the fiber optic thermometry [5]. An overview of the activities, describing experimental results, design and modelling predictions, together with the first concept and solutions for the integration of fiber optics into BRAST units, will be presented and discussed. Finally, the perspectives of the ENEA activity will be discussed.

Acknowledgments

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Reliable approach of mass production of REBCO coated conductor by using IBAD/hot-wall PLD for practical magnet applications

Y. Iijima^{1,*}, M. Ohsugi¹, K. Kakimoto¹, S. Muto¹, S. Fujita¹,
W. Hirata¹, N. Nakamura¹ and M. Daibo¹

¹Fujikura Ltd., Chiba, Japan

* Contact: yasuhiro.ijijima@jp.fujikura.com

Recent compact fusion programs have brought big demand of REBCO wires and mass production lines have rapidly been set up worldwide with production capacity of several thousand km/year [1]. So far most of them are produced by using peculiar vapor phase deposition processes as combination of thin and strong alloy substrates with buffer films textured by ion-beam-assisted deposition (IBAD), and REBCO films by pulsed-laser-deposition (PLD), both used from the early stage of REBCO coated conductor [2]. It is mainly because they are suitable to meet the critical requirement of both strong enough pinning force and large enough tensile strength for high-field application around 20 T, same as high-end NMR facilities over 1 GHz operation for which longitudinal uniformity of wire is also quite important [3].

PLD is characterized to be much supersaturated high-rate growth, resulting from fine and rapid evaporation by UV pulsed laser, creating blast wave that can reach far beyond mean free path in high enough oxygen pressure suitable for REBCO growth [4]. It allows simple growth controllability without assistance of differential pumping or chemical decomposition, etc., keeping strong flux pinning contentiously with adequate defects introduced by fast, supersaturated but good textured growth [5-6]. It brings about high production throughput and good homogeneity assisted by Hot-Wall architecture and resulting excellent production yield and capacity. Those features could shrink the equipment cost of high-power UV lasers per production length effectively.

It is also essential to improve scalability and get even lower production cost, especially for compact fusion applications, which have shorter lifetime of wires caused by strong neutron irradiation on their superconducting magnets [7]. There have been announced attractive features in chemical approaches as the potential to reach high-throughput large area deposition by chemical vapor deposition (MOCVD) [8], or very rapid growth by chemical solution deposition (CSD) [9]. But REBCO is so sensitive materials that simple PLD process is still superior for reliability and accountability of mass-production of REBCO wires to meet desired high performance, good uniformity in long piece length, with desired delivery date and acceptable cost. It is natural different approaches being simultaneously pursued for a considerable period toward the tough final goal of tremendous mass-production within low enough cost without spoiling quality control.

Fujikura group has also been increasing production capacity by using IBAD/Hot-wall PLD processes. We have REBCO wire line-ups with or without APC, possessing varied width, thickness, and protection layers. Both longitudinal and lot-to-lot uniformity of in-field I_c are quite good and mechanical strengths are strictly examined. The good uniformity of REBCO wires should also be important to establish reliable quench protection or lower AC loss, even in large-scale magnets using NI technology or not, and assembled, or striated conductors.

Acknowledgments

A part of this work is based on results performed at the High Field Laboratory for Superconducting Materials, IMR, Tohoku University.

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Irradiation Effects on High-Temperature Superconducting Coated Conductors

T. Puig¹, J. Gutierrez¹, M. Pont³, O. Traver³, A. Romanov¹, P. Krkotic^{3,4}, S. Calatroni⁴,
X. Obradors¹, L. Sedano¹, C. Torres¹, O. Mola¹, F. Sanchez², A. Morono²

¹ Insitut de Ciencia de Materials de Barcelona, ICMAB-CSIC, Bellaterra, Spain

² Centro de Investigaciones Energéticas, Medioambientales y Tecnológicas, CIEMAT, Madrid, Spain

³ ALBA Synchrotron Light Source, Barcelona, Spain

⁴ CERN, Meyrin, Switzerland

* Contact: teresa@icmab.es

High-temperature superconducting (HTS) coated conductors (CCs) are essential for compact fusion magnets, making their radiation tolerance a critical area of research. While most studies focus on 14.1 MeV neutron irradiation, HTS materials are also exposed to other high-energy particles such as electrons, alpha particles, and high energy photons, necessitating a comprehensive assessment of radiation damage tolerance.

In this study, initial studies were conducted by in-operando evaluation of superconducting properties of coated conductors under medium-high x-ray photons (>10 keV) at the ALBA synchrotron for photon fluences of about 10^{15} photons. The transition temperature, T_c and surface resistance, R_s , were evaluated and no damage was observed. Also T_c and the critical current density, J_c , were evaluated with x-ray photons of 3-20 keV, with photon fluences between 10^{10} and 10^{14} photons, and again no deterioration of the material was observed.

On-going studies include investigating the effects of irradiation on HTS films using 2 MeV electron beams from a Van de Graaff accelerator and gamma irradiation from Co-60, both at room temperature, with real-time electrical resistance monitoring. Experiments cover doses below and above 1 MGy to evaluate structural and superconducting property modifications, including defect formation and flux pinning effects. Characterization techniques, in this case, additionally include transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and normal-state charge carrier density (nH), and samples are REBCO films grown by the transient liquid assisted growth (TLAG) method developed in the group.

Future work will extend this study to in-operando superconducting-state experiments using the same radiation sources, complemented by high-energy hard x-ray photons at the ALBA synchrotron. These efforts aim to provide deeper insights into the dynamic evolution of irradiation-induced defects and their impact on HTS Coated Conductor performance.

Atomic resolution electron microscopy of defects in irradiated coated conductors

M. Coulson^{1,*}, P. Nellist¹, M. Danaie², F. Allars², C. Grovenor¹, S. Speller¹

¹ Department of Materials, University of Oxford, UK

² Diamond Light Source, Harwell Science and Innovation Campus, UK

* Contact: matthew.coulson@materials.ox.ac.uk

The superconducting transition temperature (T_c) of REBCO coated conductor is found to decrease monotonically with neutron fluence for both neutron and ion irradiation. This has been attributed to the generation of point defects throughout the REBCO lattice leading to a decrease in the superfluid density. However, this damage cannot easily be observed with atomic resolution electron microscopy STEM in HAADF mode, even in samples that have been irradiated to a high enough fluence for superconductivity to have been entirely lost, because many of the defects are believed to be in the oxygen sublattice and oxygen atoms are not strong electron scatterers. We have been exploring the use of electron ptychography using the ePSIC facility (E02) and have recently found that multi-slice techniques for reconstructing the data can successfully enable visualisation of the oxygen sublattice in these complex materials. Through careful comparison of samples irradiated with a variety of different species with unirradiated samples, we aim to gain insights using this technique on the most appropriate ion irradiation proxy for studying radiation damage in high temperature superconductors. We will also present new atomic resolution electron energy loss spectroscopy (EELS) results obtained from the E01 instrument at the ePSIC facility. Preliminary analysis of this data show that the the Cu L-edge is sensitive to differences in the Cu(1) and Cu(2) sites in REBCO, potentially making it a useful additional technique for studying irradiation defects.

HTS magnets in radiation environments at PSI: first design and planning for radiation tests

C. Calzolaio^{1,*}, A. Gabard¹, P. Guidi², and S. Sanfilippo¹

¹ Paul Scherrer Institute PSI, Switzerland

² Department of Energy, Politecnico di Torino, Italy

* Contact: ciro.calzolaio@psi.ch

The Paul Scherrer Institute (PSI) operates the world's most powerful proton cyclotron. Currently, all magnets are resistive and require about 2.6 MW of power. Due to the high level of radiation, about 20 per cent of the magnets are designed to be radiation-resistant, which means that they do not rely on any organic impregnation and use compacted MgO powder as an insulator. Although these magnets have proven to be very reliable, they are limited to magnetic fields below 2 T and consume a lot of electricity. Energy efficiency is nowadays a crucial concern for the accelerator community, prompting an exploration of alternative solutions to resistive magnets. Superconducting magnets could be a viable, energy-efficient alternative for both primary and secondary beamlines of large accelerator facilities. To investigate this possibility, we plan several different measurements using the available infrastructure at PSI.

Use of the proton cyclotron as parasitic source of radiation. In this contest we plan to:

- Install of a superconducting demonstrator magnet based on ReBCO coils close to the cyclotron. The aim is to study the effect of radiation both on the HTS conductor itself and on all the magnet components surrounding it. Critical current and temperature will be periodically measured over time at different absorbed dose.
- Install several ReBCO short samples close to the target to be irradiated at room temperature.

Use of dedicated irradiation facilities at PSI:

- Irradiation of short samples and coils using the Proton Irradiation Facility with a maximum fluence of 10^{13} p/cm². It will be possible to irradiate samples in a liquid nitrogen bath.
- Irradiation of short samples and coils using the gantries for proton therapy (irradiation in liquid nitrogen to be checked).
- Neutron irradiation of short samples using the Neutron Irradiation Service (NIS) which provides mainly thermal neutrons with a flux of 2.8×10^{13} n/cm²/s.

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The Radiation Environment in a Spherical Tokamak Fusion Pilot Plant

C. Wilson^{1,*}, K. Chandrasekhar¹, and M. Rajput¹

¹ Tokamak Energy, Milton Park, Abingdon, United Kingdom

* Contact: chris.wilson@tokamakenergy.com

Tokamak Energy is an awardee of the US Department of Energy's Milestone-Based Fusion Development Program and is developing a pre-concept design of a Fusion Pilot Plant (FPP) under the first phase of funding. Tokamak Energy's FPP is a plant capable of demonstrating the generation of 50 MW net electrical power, with a full power life of 5 years. At the heart of the FPP is a Spherical Tokamak (ST) fusion device that efficiently utilises High-Temperature Superconductors (HTS) to provide strong magnetic fields for plasma confinement and control. The life-limiting factor of the plant is the neutron-induced degradation of the critical current of the HTS when exposed to the radiation environment within the tokamak. During the pre-concept design neutronics models of the tokamak have been generated to substantiate the lifetime requirement, as well as determining the nuclear heat load on the HTS coils and their supporting cold mass to inform the capacity and design of the cryogenic cooling system. Detailed 3D maps of neutron and gamma-ray flux across the tokamak are presented and differential flux spectra on the HTS system are shown. A study of the nuclear effects on HTS, including heating, transmutation, gas production, primary knock-on atom spectra and displacement damage are presented, to inform future laboratory-based experimental campaigns and modelling of microscopic effects.

Figure 1: Fast ($E > 0.1\text{MeV}$) neutron flux on the magnet cage of a Fusion Pilot Plant

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Irradiation effects on high temperature superconductors in advanced-fuel compact tokamaks

A. Morandi¹, D. Pettinari¹ and M. Zucchetti^{1,*}

¹ Department of Energy, Politecnico di Torino, Italy

* Contact: massimo.zucchetti@polito.it

Recent advancements in high-temperature superconducting (HTS) magnets have enabled tokamaks to reduce dimensions and operate with higher plasma parameters. This opens to the possibility of using advanced fuel mixtures such as Deuterium–Helium3 (DHe³). Compared to traditional fuels, DHe³ offers the potential to reduce neutron-induced activation and minimize the presence of tritium in the fuel cycle: however, achieving the high plasma parameters required for ignition is a challenge, and DHe³ is also too rare on Earth. Advancements in (HTS magnets and the establishment of a lunar economy to extract ³Helium from the surface of the Moon could potentially solve these problems.

This paper is focused on how DHe³ fusion can be exploited to reduce the neutron flux in a high-field tokamak. The primary focus is to compare the performance, regarding radiation damage on toroidal field coils magnets, of DT and DHe³ fuel mixtures. The design considered in this study is an Affordable, Robust, Compact (ARC)-class tokamak, equipped with a 2LiF+BeF₂ (FLiBe) liquid immersion breeding blanket. This material provides efficient breeding, shielding and activation characteristics, but may present some problems regarding materials compatibility and costs.

While a first comparison has been carried out using for the DHe³ configuration a FLiBe-like blanket, alternative blanket configurations have been explored. A borated-water blanket, a simple solution aimed just at absorbing neutrons, has been examined. However, a clear advantage of an advanced-fuel tokamak is that you do not need to breed any tritium, so you can reduce the radial thickness of the blanket, just to perform some neutron shielding, if necessary: in this way, you can have the magnets much closer to the plasma than for a DT tokamak, with the welcomed result of obtaining higher magnetic fields in the plasma region, a very welcome feature for burning DHe³.

A neutronic model has been set up, by means of the OpenMC code: it is a refinement of the model that has been used in previous works by the authors, with focus on neutron flux and radiation damage on the TFCs.

In this study, we showed that using DHe³ fuel at a temperature of 69 keV and an electron density of $1.3e^{14} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ reduces the total neutron flux on the inboard TF coils by 30 times, compared to DT fuel. This would solve all the radiation damage problems for those components (see Figure 1)

Looking forward, the integration of novel reactor designs and optimization strategies —such as spin-polarized fuels to boost fusion reaction rates, operating in the plasma’s second stability region, and exploring direct energy conversion should be considered to enhance the feasibility of DHe³ fusion.

Fig. 1 - Total neutron fluxes [n/cm²/s]

Fusion magnet quench risk increase with irradiation damage

J. M. John^{1,*}, M. R. Gilbert¹, and C. D. Hardie¹

¹UKAEA, Abingdon, Oxfordshire, OX14 3DB, UK

* Contact: jacob.john@ukaea.uk

Superconducting material enables fusion reactor magnet concepts to operate with current densities that would melt materials with non-zero resistance. The application of superconducting material is considered essential for net-positive power machines. Catastrophic damage can occur when superconductivity is lost and the current generates heat. This scenario is called a quench. Stabilizer material carries the magnet current (typically copper) during a quench and is the focus of this work. Irradiation-induced defects store energy in the Cu crystalline lattice. The presence of defects reduces thermal conductivity (thermally insulating the superconductor), electrical conductivity (increasing temperature ramp rate during a quench), and specific heat capacity (increasing thermodynamic instability). The release of stored energy in the magnet materials, in combination with the magnet material property changes, has the potential to cause extreme off-normal events in superconducting magnets that worsen with fluence. Stored energy can be released causing local heating and increasing the risk of a quench. For example, following irradiation at 4.6 K and a fluence of 0.45×10^{18} n/cm², an energy release of 0.023 J/g was measured from Cu when increased in temperature from 10 K to 18 K, which would have been enough energy to create the same temperature increase spontaneously. Extrapolations of experimental data are used to estimate when spontaneous heating can occur due to the release of energy stored in irradiation-induced defects. Critical fluence values are estimated between 1.74×10^{18} n/cm² and 2.85×10^{19} n/cm² (figure 1) for neutron irradiation of Cu at a temperature of 20 K. In-situ cryogenic calorimetry experiments, operated at high-temperature-ramp rates on irradiated magnet materials, could offer certainty for fusion magnet system designers. Periodic annealing of defects through controlled temperature cycling will be essential in fusion power plants to manage the increasing risk of quench as the superconducting magnets accumulate dose. The ideal frequency and dynamics of these maintenance temperature cycles will be established with further experimental examination.

Figure 1: Temperature margin reduction with fluence resulting from Wigner energy release in the magnet's stabilizer material. Dotted line accounts for reduction in HTS performance.

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Time Domain Reflectometry (TDR) measurements for quench detection in HTS tapes

A. Trotta¹, F. Beggio¹, and M. De Bastiani¹

¹ Eni S.p.A, Marghera, Italy

* Contact: antonio.trotta@eni.com

The discovery of high critical temperature superconductors (HTS) has opened the door to a series of new applications, both in the scientific and social fields, for superconductivity. Among the most relevant are experiments in physics, nuclear fusion and electrical power transmission.

One of the aspects that most limits the diffusion of this technology is the protection from the “quench”, a technical term that defines the unexpected and violent transition to the resistive state of the superconductor. This phenomenon is typically destructive for the device and therefore requires the presence of active systems for protection.

The quench generally originates in a limited portion of the volume, due to defects, or external disturbances, and its detection is more effective the earlier it occurs with respect to the propagation of the quench. The aim of this project is therefore to investigate the feasibility of using reflectometry techniques, borrowed from defect detection systems for traditional conductors, for the detection of quench in devices based on HTS.

Cable reflectometry, also known as Time Domain Reflectometry (TDR), is a technique used to locate defects and assess the integrity of cables. It works by sending a pulse along the cable; when the pulse encounters a discontinuity (such as a defect or break), it is reflected back. By analyzing the return time and the shape of the reflected pulse, the location and nature of the problem can be determined. This technique is useful for locating breaks, short circuits, and measuring cable lengths. Typically, pulses no longer than 1 ns are used, or signals with frequencies between 1 MHz and 1 GHz (see Figure 1).

Superconductors have historically been used for direct current (DC) or low frequency applications, mainly due to the high dissipation induced by time-varying fields and currents. Studies on the behaviour of HTS at frequencies comparable to those of TDR are few and the applications are limited to accelerating cavities and beam screens for accelerators. The use of frequencies in the range of MHz and GHz on superconductors is considered particularly challenging: the signal travels on the surface of the stabilizer, not reaching the superconductor inside.

The project is intended as a proof of principle, aimed at experimentally investigating the behaviour of HTS tapes subjected to TDR. In this phase, the aim is therefore to replicate with an HTS conductor the typical conditions of a reflectometry test, introducing an artificial defect. The aim is therefore to observe a reflected signal due to the quench effect, visible in the heating of the stabilizing copper inside the tape, as a means of wave propagation.

Figure 1: operating diagram of a reflectometry system for electric cables.

Neutron Irradiation Tolerant REBCO Tapes for Compact Fusion Reactors

V. Selvamanickam^{1,2,*}, B. Sarangi¹, D. X. Fischer³, and K. B. Woller³

¹Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, Advanced Manufacturing Institute, Texas Center for Superconductivity, University of Houston, Houston, USA

²AMPeers LLC, Houston, USA

³Department of Nuclear Engineering, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Boston, USA

* Contact: selva@uh.edu

The ultra-high critical magnetic fields of RE-Ba-Cu-O (REBCO RE=rare earth) High Temperature Superconductors (HTS) are very attractive for compact fusion energy systems that can operate over a temperature range of 4 – 50 K in magnetic fields beyond the realm of Nb₃Sn wires. REBCO tapes are now being manufactured in piece lengths of few hundred meters with critical current (I_c) of 150 A/4mm at 20 K, 20 T.

The normalized critical current of commercial REBCO tapes at 30 K, 15 T has been found to increase at intermediate levels of neutron fluence, before decreasing sharply at levels above $3 \times 10^{22} \text{ m}^{-2}$ [1]. A major concern is that the neutron flux typical of a tokamak, and particularly a compact tokamak, may lead to significant degradation of REBCO tape performance if this issue is not addressed. This effectively sets a minimum amount of shielding and a minimum device size and cost; or, equivalently, for a given device size, it sets device lifetime. However, despite its importance, a systematic study of the effects of tape composition and structure on tape robustness under neutron irradiation has not been carried out. Commercial REBCO tapes, originally developed for electric power applications, have not been properly optimized for high magnetic field applications and not at all designed for neutron irradiation tolerance.

We have identified compositions of undoped and Zr-doped REBCO tapes with superior irradiation tolerance. Using proton irradiation as a proxy for neutron irradiation to expedite feedback to materials optimization without the long delays of neutron irradiation testing, we identified at least four compositions where the degradation in critical current density (J_c) below the unirradiated level was extended beyond the goal of 3.3x i.e. a proton fluence of $6.6 \times 10^{20} \text{ p/m}^2$. The same REBCO tapes that showed superior tolerance to proton irradiation performed better than the commercial tape under neutron irradiation up to $1 \times 10^{22} \text{ n/m}^2$. We have also explored integration of neutron shielding in commercial REBCO tapes using MgB₂-coated copper laminates.

The results of our project on the development of neutron irradiation tolerant REBCO tapes will be discussed in this presentation.

Acknowledgments

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(Im-?)possible prediction of performance change of coated conductors in fusion magnets

M. Eisterer^{1,*}, R. Unterrainer¹, and A. Bodenseher¹

¹ Atominstitut, TU Wien, Vienna, Austria

* Contact: michael.eisterer@tuwien.ac.at

Irradiation damage is a concern for fusion magnets made of high-temperature superconductors due to their degradation resulting from the defects introduced by high-energy particles. Current efforts focus on the prediction of the radiation environment at the magnet location, the expected defect structure and the resulting change in superconducting properties. While the radiation environment has to be predicted by numerical simulations, the expected degradation may be obtained from a combination of modelling and experiments. However, a conclusive “how to do” is still missing. The predicted radiation environments in fusion magnets consist predominantly of neutrons but also of protons and electrons with energies ranging from below 1 keV to more than 14 MeV [1,2]. These radiation environments are not available in experiments; thus, one is restricted to irradiation experiments with neutrons with a different energy distribution or (typically mono-energetic) proxy particles (neutrons, protons, ions). The resulting defect structure depends on both, the type of particle and its energy. To complicate the situation further, large defects rather enhance the critical current due to flux pinning (true?) while small defects seem the main driver for the degradation [3], because they efficiently enhance pair-breaking scattering reducing both, the critical current density and the transition temperature, leading to a close correlation between these two quantities (and the normal state resistivity) [4]. This does not help too much, because neither changes of the normal state resistivity nor the transition temperature can be related to microstructural disorder quantitatively so far (which is hard to assess experimentally anyway).

The aim of the talk is to provoke a discussion rather than presenting new results. Is it worth the effort to predict the introduced defect landscape? Is it realistic to predict the performance change based on numerical simulations? Are benchmarking experiments with particles of particular energies better suited for this purpose?

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The Effect of Filtered Oxygen Ion Irradiation on the Critical Properties of REBCO Coated Conductors

W. Ilyffe^{1,*}, S. Chislett-McDonald², K. Adams², S. Speller², C. Grovenor²,
S. Wimbush³, and E. Nassr³

¹ United Kingdom Atomic Energy Authority, Culham Campus, Abingdon, Oxfordshire, OX14 3DB, United Kingdom

² Oxford University Material Department, Parks Road, Oxford, OX1 3PH, United Kingdom

³ United Kingdom Industrial Fusion Solutions Ltd, Culham Campus, Abingdon, Oxfordshire, OX14 3DB, United Kingdom

* Contact: william.ilyffe@ukaea.uk

The economic viability of fusion power plants such as UK Industrial Fusion Solutions' Spherical Tokamak for Energy Production (STEP) [1] is a function of their size, toroidal field (TF) strength and availability throughout their operating lifetime [2]. Cost optimisation has led STEP to adopt a compact design featuring TF cables comprising a stack of rare-earth barium copper oxide (REBCO) coated conductors (CC), given its excellent current carrying capacity at low temperature and high field [3]. However, neutron irradiation leads to changes in the superconducting properties of REBCO [4] which in turn the operating lifetime of tokamaks [5]. The STEP team developed a plan to characterise the superconducting properties of REBCO CC under representative fusion conditions [6], making progress as described in [7]. In this work, several commercially available REBCO CC were oxygen ion irradiated in steps of $\approx 10^{-3}$ displacement per atom (dpa) up to and beyond STEP relevant damage levels. The irradiation used an energy filter [8] to more closely mimic the effects of fusion-spectrum neutrons. After each step, critical current density, critical temperature and irreversibility line were measured, allowing changes in these properties to be tracked with changing damage level. Results show that the choice of rare-earth in REBCO affects both the starting critical temperature and the rate of its monotonic decline with damage level. Results also show that measurement temperature and field strength perpendicular to the tape plane affect the trajectory of the change in critical current density of REBCO with damage level, and that this trajectory can be modelled as a combination of changing pinning efficiency and a loss in superconducting volume.

In this presentation, the irradiation method and results are presented and discussed, along with the implications for the design of the STEP and tokamaks in general.

Acknowledgements

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Defect annealing experiments on neutron irradiated coated conductors: Identifying harmful defects and optimizing heat treatments for performance recovery

A. Bodenseher^{1,*}, D. Hackl¹, R. Unterrainer¹, and M. Eisterer¹

¹ Atominstitut, TU Wien, Vienna, Austria

* Contact: alexander.bodenseher@tuwien.ac.at

Neutrons produced by nuclear fusion reactions introduce defects into the superconductors in the magnet system. This limits the lifetime of the magnet system, impeding economic viability. One approach to mitigate this effect is to increase the size of the reactor and strategically place shielding material in especially affected areas. Another one is thermally treating the magnet system during maintenance windows. The reported recovery with annealing [1], motivates further study into the interplay between the superconducting properties and specific defects and recovery of the former.

Samples based on commercial coated conductors were pre-characterized and then irradiated with neutrons in a TRIGA Mark II research reactor until the critical current degraded beyond the initial pristine value – also referred as crossover disorder – corresponding to a decrease of the critical temperature of up to 8 K. In order to measure the resistance of the REBCO layer, the silver stabilizing layer was removed by chemical etching between the voltage contacts.

The samples were then subjected to thermal treatment in pure oxygen atmosphere and two annealing procedures were devised. Isothermal annealing, where the annealing time was increased step by step, until no recovery of the critical temperature and critical current was observed. Additionally, continuous temperature sweeps up to 400 °C were conducted on the etched samples during which the resistivity was measured in situ. This study compares features in the temperature dependence of the resistivity to predicted defect formation/recombination energies and mobilities. The respective recovery of the critical temperature are utilized in order to identify the defect species that are particularly harmful for the superconducting properties.

Building on these results, we present the capabilities of neutron irradiated high temperature superconductors to recover, possibly extending the life of future compact fusion devices, which is an important foundation for the future design of fusion reactors.

Acknowledgments

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Cryogenic ion irradiation of high-temperature superconductors with *in situ* positron spectroscopy & AC susceptibility measurements of critical temperature

A. R. Devitre^{1,*}, P. Amoroso², I. Zhelezova², L. Civale³, D. X. Fischer¹,
S. Chamberlain¹, W. Burke¹, K. Helariutta², J. Slotte², M. P. Short¹, Z. S. Hartwig¹

¹Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Cambridge, MA, USA

²University of Helsinki, FI

³University of Connecticut, Mansfield, CT, USA

* Contact: devitre@mit.edu

Superconducting magnets made of yttrium barium copper oxide (YBCO) tapes enable compact power plant designs, which have accelerated the commercialization of fusion energy. Efforts to understand the radiation tolerance of YBCO have culminated in a hypothesis, formulated by Eisterer, stating that critical current density (J_c) declines as radiation-induced defects accumulate and enhance Cooper pair scattering (ρ). In this model, ρ is proportional to the change in critical temperature, ΔT_c . However, all experiments to date have measured *either* the superconducting properties *or* the microstructure. Moreover, the vast majority of data proceeds from irradiations conducted above 300 K; not representative of the fusion environment. We present a first attempt to measure T_c and characterize the defect landscape *simultaneously*. We irradiated YBCO crystals ($4 \times 4 \times 0.25 \text{ mm}^3$, twin density $< 10\%$) at 33 K with 10 MeV protons and measured the mean positron lifetime (MLT) to quantify the amount of open-volume defects without warming up the sample. We find microstructural evidence for a defect recovery threshold between 100 and 200 K, consistent with recent tape annealing, where J_c and T_c show an increase $> 5\%$ of their post-irradiation value. We present the results of the latest campaign: where ΔT_c and MLT are measured in-situ, between irradiation and isochronal anneal steps, with an outlook on the possibility of testing the theoretical prediction of Eisterer. If confirmed, this model will become an essential design tool to set the minimum neutron shield thickness needed to achieve reliable, economical fusion electricity production.

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Cryogenic irradiation capabilities for testing fusion magnet materials at MIT

D. X. Fischer^{1,*}, A. R. Devitre¹, K. B. Woller¹, Z. L. Fisher¹, Z. S. Hartwig¹

¹ Plasma Science and Fusion Center, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Cambridge, USA

* Contact: dafisch@mit.edu

Fusion magnets will operate in a harsh environment of hard neutron radiation. This degrades the microstructure of functional components such as superconductors, insulators, and sensors, ultimately compromising their performance and longevity.

The current estimate for the radiation limit of REBCO tapes is about $3 \times 10^{22} \text{ m}^{-2}$, based on room-temperature irradiation results. However, REBCO fusion magnets are subject to radiation damage at their operational temperature of around 20 K. To investigate the effects of low-temperature irradiation, we used MIT's cryogenic ion irradiation setup to expose REBCO tapes to 1.2 MeV protons. For irradiations at 20 K, we observed a 40% higher degradation rate of all investigated superconducting parameters compared to irradiations at 300 K. This might suggest that the observed reductions of critical current, n-value, and transition temperature can all be traced back to the same origin - the breaking of Cooper pairs caused by scattering at small defects.

Our results further indicate that fusion magnets could already cease operation at fast neutron fluences of $2 \times 10^{22} \text{ m}^{-2}$, given the accelerated defect accumulation at low temperatures. We showcase the new cryogenic neutron irradiation facility, currently under construction at the MIT reactor, which will allow to investigate the actual fluence limits of REBCO tapes and other fusion magnet components under realistic conditions.

Computational modelling of radiation damage in high-temperature superconductors: from reactor's design to damage at the atomistic level

D. Gambino^{1,2,3,*}, F. Ledda^{3,4}, N. Di Eugenio^{3,4}, A. Dickson⁵, V. Jantunen², K. Nordlund², D. Torsello^{3,4}, F. Djurabekova², S. T. Murphy⁵, and F. Laviano^{3,4}

¹ Department of Physics, Chemistry, and Biology (IFM), Linköping University, Sweden

² Department of Physics, University of Helsinki, Finland

³ Department of Applied Science and Technology, Politecnico di Torino, Italy

⁴ INFN - Sez. Torino, Italy

⁵ Engineering Department, Lancaster University, UK

* Contact: davide.gambino@liu.se

Understanding of radiation damage in high-temperature superconductors (HTS) is key to designing compact fusion reactors that can operate for sufficient time. Recent estimates predict very short operation times before the superconducting properties of the HTS magnets are completely destroyed by irradiation with energetic particles [1], suggesting the need of thick screens that would reduce the compactness of the reactor. Since experimental investigations are currently not able to reproduce the radiation environment of such reactors, computational modelling can guide the design of such reactors to withstand the harsh conditions. In this talk, I will discuss our workflow [2] for the prediction of radiation damage in HTS magnets (Fig. 1). We start from a model of the reactor, imported from a CAD model [3], from which we obtain the neutron spectrum at the HTS magnet with neutronics Monte Carlo simulations and the spectrum of primary knock-on atoms (PKA) in the material. Knowing the PKA spectrum, we carry out molecular dynamics (MD) simulations at different recoil energies to obtain information on the number of defects produced, the size of the defect clusters or cascades, and their morphology as a function of energy. A review of our own results and results from literature will be presented in order to summarize the current knowledge of radiation damage in HTS from computational methods. Finally, I will propose quantities that can be calculated from simulations and compared directly with experiments, enabling a complete benchmark of the computational models and establishing the accuracy and reliability of properties predicted using this workflow.

Figure 1: Workflow for the investigation of radiation damage in HTS magnets from design of the reactor to atomistic damage.

Acknowledgments

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Ion irradiation effect on the in-field performance of MOD-REBCO coated conductors

Z. Ning^{1,2,*}, L. Zhiyong^{1,2}, H. Rongtie^{1,2}, Z. Difan^{1,2}, C. Jing^{1,2},
G. Yanqun^{1,2}, L. Li³, and C. Chuanbing^{1,2}

¹ Shanghai Key Laboratory of High Temperature Superconductors, Department of Physics, Shanghai University, Shanghai, China

² Shanghai Creative Superconductor Technologies Co. Ltd., Shanghai, China

³ Institute of Modern Physics, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Lanzhou, China

* Contact: ningzhang@shu.edu.cn

This study investigates the effects of He-ion irradiation on the in-field performance of nanocrystal-added REBa₂Cu₃O_{7-δ} (REBCO; RE = Y, rare earth element) superconductors at 4.2 K, focusing on the influence of nano-addition concentration on critical current enhancement. Experimental results demonstrate that REBCO with low nanocrystal adding exhibits a 1.68 times increase in the critical current (I_c) at 3 Tesla, while highly added samples show only a 1.18 times improvement, indicating a more pronounced response to irradiation in low-added samples. Additionally, as the irradiation dose increases, the in-field performance enhancement advantages of high-dose irradiation become more apparent, with extrapolated results suggesting greater potential for in-field performance of REBCO improvement under high-dose ion irradiation conditions. This finding reveals the complex interplay between nanocrystal concentration and irradiation dose, providing new insights for optimizing REBCO superconductor performance in high magnetic fields. The results hold significant importance for understanding the synergistic mechanisms between irradiation-induced defects and nanostructures, offering experimental evidence for the development of high-performance superconducting materials.

Comparative analysis of low-energy ion irradiation on superconducting properties of GdBa₂Cu₃O_y coated conductors

T. Ozaki^{1,*}, H. Okazaki², H. Koshikawa², S. Yamamoto², M. Saeki²,
 T. Yamaki², T. Sueyoshi³, and H. Sakane⁴

¹ School of Engineering, Kwansei Gakuin University, Sanda, Japan

² Takasaki Institute for Advanced Quantum Science, National Institutes for Quantum Science and Technology, Takasaki, Japan

³ Kyushu Sangyo University, Fukuoka, Japan

⁴ SHI-ATEX Co. Ltd., Saijyo, Japan

* Contact: tozaki@kwansei.ac.jp

High-temperature superconducting REBa₂Cu₃O_y (REBCO, RE: Y and rare earth) coated conductors (CCs) with high critical current density J_c in magnetic fields would enable to operate nuclear fusion reactors at higher temperatures, which could lead to a reduction of cooling requirements and a more compact design. The high in-field J_c could be obtained by introducing precipitates and defects with nano-meter size in superconducting materials, which can pin the vortices.[1] Ion irradiation is a well-established method for introducing various defects into superconducting materials in a fairly predictable and controllable fashion by choosing appropriate ion species and irradiation energy.[2,3] Recently, a low-energy ion irradiation has been revisited as a feasible approach to improve vortex pinning in REBCO films.[1-3] In this study, we present comparative analysis of low-energy ion irradiation on superconducting properties of GdBCO CCs.

Figure 1 shows superconducting transition temperature T_c as a function of fluence in GdBCO CCs irradiated with 350 keV Ar-ions. The T_c 's of the GdBCO CCs irradiated with 350 keV Ar-ions gradually decrease with increasing fluence up to around 1.0×10^{13} ions/cm², corresponding to 0.0060 dpa (dpa: displacement per atom) and then significantly started to drop. Figure 2 exhibits the magnetic field dependence of the J_c enhancement, $(J_c^{\text{after}} - J_c^{\text{before}})/J_c^{\text{before}}$, with $H//c$ for GdBCO CCs irradiated with 350 keV Ar-ions at 30 K. We found that the 350 keV Ar-ion irradiation yields up to over 50% J_c increase over 3 T at 30 K. These results indicate that the 350 keV Ar-ion irradiation would be effective for an in-field J_c enhancement in GdBCO CCs. We will also report several results on GdBCO CCs irradiated with several ions (H⁺, He⁺, Ar⁺, Cu²⁺, ...) and future experiments about ion irradiations at low temperature and in-situ measurements of superconducting properties.

Figure 1: T_c vs fluence for GdBCO CCs irradiated with 350 keV Ar-ions

Figure 2: J_c enhancement as a function of the magnetic field for GdBCO CCs irradiated with 350 keV Ar-ions.

Acknowledgments

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Exploring the Impact of Irradiation Dose on Shaping the Superconducting Performance of $\text{EuBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{7-d}$

D. Gong^{1,*}

¹ Institute of Electrical Engineering, Chinese Academy of Sciences, China

* Contact: dgong@mail.iee.ac.cn

Manipulating pinning centers via irradiation has been recognized as a powerful technique for optimizing superconducting properties. The type, dose, and energy of irradiating particles determine the nature of the defects formed in the material, each influencing superconducting properties in distinct ways.

Here, by tuning the Xe irradiation dose within the range of 10^{10} to 10^{12} , we reveal the impact of irradiation dose on the superconducting performance of $\text{EuBa}_2\text{Cu}_2\text{O}_{7-\delta}$ (EBCO) across different magnetic field ranges. A lower dose (10^{10} ions/cm²) enhances critical current at low-field (below 1T), while moderate doses (10^{11} ions/cm²) improve critical current at high-field. By further increasing the doses up to 10^{12} ions/cm², superconductivity is significantly suppressed due to oxygen disordering, as evidenced by Raman spectra. More interestingly, these behaviors show weak dependence on both the temperature and thickness of EBCO.

This work shows a promising avenue to effectively manipulate superconducting performance through irradiation dose, particularly for applications under magnetic field.

Combined Approach for Atomistic Modeling of Radiation Damage in YBCO

F. Ledda^{1,2,3*}, D. Gambino^{1,3,4}, N. Di Eugenio^{1,2}, V. Jantunen³, K. Nordlund³, D. Torsello^{1,2},
F. Djurabekova³, F. Laviano^{1,2}

¹ Politecnico di Torino, Department of Applied Science and Technology, Italy

² Istituto Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare, Sezione di Torino, Italy

³ Department of Physics, University of Helsinki, Finland

⁴ Department of Physics, Chemistry, and Biology (IFM), Linköping University, Sweden

* Contact: federico.ledda@polito.it

Compact tokamaks have the potential to speed up the development of cost-effective fusion energy, thanks to their reduced expenses and quicker construction timelines [1]. High temperature superconductors have quickly become a pivotal technology in this area, allowing for the production of stronger magnetic fields necessary to downsize the reactor while preserving the plasma power [2].

Nonetheless, the compact design introduces new challenges—most notably, heightened neutron irradiation of the magnets. This exposure produces defects and structural changes that can impair superconducting performance and reduce the overall lifespan of the system [3][4]. Since replicating these conditions in experiments is highly complex, computational approaches are essential for uncovering the microscopic mechanisms of degradation, serving as powerful tools in the development of effective mitigation strategies [5].

In this work, we present our combined approach for modelling radiation-induced damage in $\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{7-x}$ (YBCO), using molecular dynamics (MD) and binary collision approximation (BCA) simulations (Figure 1). For various primary knockon atoms (PKAs), we analyzed multiple collision cascades at energies below 10 keV with MD, assessing both the number and morphology of resulting defects. To extend our study to higher energy ranges, we determined accurate threshold displacement energies considering different crystallographic sites, enabling further investigation via BCA. By combining these results with recoil spectra, our methodology provides a framework for quantifying radiation damage through atomistic simulations tailored to any given radiation environment.

Figure 1. Combined approach for modelling radiation damage in YBCO. Schematic representation of the defects

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Machine-Learning Interatomic Potentials for Radiation Damage Analysis in High-Temperature Superconductors

N. Di Eugenio^{1,2,*}, A. Dickson³, D. Gambino^{1,4,5}, D. Torsello^{1,2},
F. Ledda^{1,2,5}, F. Djurabekova⁵, S. Murphy², and F. Laviano^{1,2}

¹ Politecnico di Torino, Department of Applied Science and Technology, Italy

² Istituto Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare, Sezione di Torino, Italy

³ Department of Engineering, Lancaster University, Lancaster, United Kingdom

⁴ Department of Physics, Chemistry, and Biology (IFM), Linköping University, Sweden

⁵ Department of Physics, University of Helsinki, Finland

* Contact: niccolo.dieugenio@polito.it

The superconducting properties of rare-earth barium copper oxides (REBCOs) materials such as $\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{7-x}$ (YBCO) are subject to profound changes when crystal defects are present. Neutron irradiation in compact fusion reactors for example leads to structural damage and degradation of such superconducting properties. Atomistic simulations can thus provide insight into the microscopic features of radiation damage, suggesting strategies for guaranteeing performances [1]. Radiation damage can be modeled by means of Molecular Dynamics (MD) simulations of collision cascades, relying on an interatomic potential that was developed for such analysis [2]. Despite the good performances of this potential, in order to improve the description of interatomic interactions even further, the development of a Machine Learning Potential (MLP) framework [3] can lead to simulations of unprecedented accuracy.

To this goal, I will present our work on MLPs for radiation damage analysis, starting from Density Functional Theory (DFT) calculations with the CP2K [4] software of various YBCO structures, starting from ideal, energy-minimized configurations of different YBCO stoichiometries and of YBCO sub-phases, to then perform volume, strain and random distortions on the obtained supercells. In addition, defected $\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_7$ configurations were also obtained by introducing vacancies, interstitials and Frenkel pairs. Finally, melted configurations were also included. The creation of an extended dataset is functional to the training of suitable MLP descriptors, such as MACE [5], ACE [6], GAP [7] and tab-GAP [8]. I will thus show the results obtained with MACE and ACE, starting from the statistical analysis of their trainings and validation on different datasets. I will then move to testing and comparing the results obtained with each descriptor when evaluating several physical properties, like lattice parameters values through thermal expansion MD runs, the energy-volume equation of state (in both the relaxed and unrelaxed case), the defects' formation energy and Frenkel pairs' energy barrier through Nudged Elastic Bands (NEB) simulations [9]. In addition, I will also show phonon dispersion relations, dimer repulsion energies, binding energy of vacancies, and other important thermodynamic quantities. Promising aspects of MACE like the computation of spectral properties will also be discussed [10].

Acknowledgments

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A high-fidelity machine learned interatomic potential for simulating radiation damage in $\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_7$

A. Dickson^{1,*}, N. Di Eugenio^{3,4}, D. Gambino^{2,3,5}, D. Torsello^{3,4}, S. Murphy¹, F. Djurabekova²,
F. Laviano^{3,4}, M. Gilbert⁶, D. Nguyen-Manh⁶

¹ Department of Engineering, Lancaster University, U.K.

² Department of Physics, University of Helsinki, Finland

³ Politecnico di Torino, Department of Applied Science and Technology, Italy

⁴ Istituto Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare, Sezione di Torino, Italy

⁵ Department of Physics, Chemistry, and Biology (IFM), Linköping University, Sweden

⁶ UK Atomic Energy Authority (UKAEA), Culham campus, U.K.

* Contact: a.dickson2@lancaster.ac.uk

High-temperature superconductors (HTS) are promising materials for next-generation fusion reactors, owing to their remarkable magnetic field strengths at elevated temperatures. However, the extent of radiation induced damage in these materials under operational conditions is poorly understood. Direct experimental observation of in operando damage processes is challenging, therefore, there is an increased reliance on modelling. Atomistic simulation techniques, such as Molecular Dynamics (MD), enable the study of a material's structural response to neutron irradiation, providing an atomic level description of the amount and nature of the damage created. In this context we employ molecular dynamics (MD) simulations to predict the structural response of $\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_7$ (YBCO) to neutron irradiation. Key to the efficacy of MD models is being able to accurately replicate the interactions between the ions in the system.

Machine-learned potentials (MLPs) offer the accuracy of an electronic structure approach, such as Density Functional Theory, at a fraction of the computational cost, making them ideal for modelling radiation damage processes that occur on time and length scales beyond the reach of electronic structure approaches. Here, we develop and validate a high-fidelity tabulated Gaussian Approximation Potential (tabGAP) for $\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_7$, trained on a diverse dataset that ensures accurate representation of atomic interactions in the highly disordered heat-spike of a collision cascade. This model will enable more reliable predictions of fusion-relevant damage in HTS materials, providing important insight into the shielding requirements of future fusion devices. We present preliminary results obtained with this potential, including thermodynamic, physical, and spectral properties. Additionally, we demonstrate its application in representative radiation damage simulations.

Impact of oxygen content on defect formation and diffusion in $\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{7-\delta}$: A first-principles study

L. Yang^{1,2,*} and B. D. Wirth^{2,3}

¹ UT-Oak Ridge Innovation Institute, University of Tennessee, Knoxville, USA

² Department of Nuclear Engineering, University of Tennessee, Knoxville, USA

³ Fusion Energy Division, Oak Ridge National Laboratory, Oak Ridge, USA

* Contact: liyang@utk.edu

High temperature superconducting (HTS) magnet materials, such as $\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{7-\delta}$, are a key component of advanced fusion reactor designs. Degradation resulting from high energy neutron exposure, and corresponding defect production and evolution, will determine the usable lifetime of HTS in the fusion environment. First-principles density functional theory (DFT) calculations have been used to investigate the energetics of point defects in $\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{7-\delta}$. To understand the effect of oxygen content on defect formation and diffusion, several oxygen contents ($\delta = 0.0-0.5$) have been considered. Regardless of oxygen content, the formation energies of point defects indicate oxygen defects are dominant, followed by Cu defects. Ba and Y defects are less energetically favourable. At $\delta = 0.0$, oxygen will diffuse along the b-axis on basal planes via a vacancy mechanism. Oxygen can diffuse on the basal plane via either an interstitial or vacancy mechanism and can diffuse along the c-axis at relatively high temperatures. Excess Ba and Y will create antisite defects and Cu interstitials, rather than being at interstitial positions. Cu interstitials can diffuse in bulk $\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_7$ with an energy of ~ 1.1 eV. Cation vacancies are much less mobile than the corresponding interstitials and oxygen vacancies. For $\delta > 0$, the oxygen vacancies in $\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{7-\delta}$ will align along the b-axis on the basal planes. The effect of oxygen content on defect behaviour has been investigated systematically. The aim of this study is to predict the effect of oxygen content on the irradiation stability of HTS magnet materials as a first step in understanding radiation-induced defects required to accelerate the qualification of HTS magnet materials for fusion applications.

Fusion relevant gamma irradiation test of commercial HTS and lab-scale YBCO film: towards in situ measurements

V. Pinto^{1,*}, A. Masi¹, V. Colasanti^{1,2}, A. Cemmi³, R. Carcione³, A. Verna³, I. Di Sarcina³, J. Scifo³, M. De Angelis^{1,2}, M. Tomellini², F. Laviano^{4,5}, D. Torsello^{4,5}, and G. Celentano¹

¹ Superconductivity Laboratory, Nuclear Department, ENEA, Frascati, Italy

² Tor Vergata University, Dept. of Chemical Sciences and Technologies, Rome, Italy

³ Gamma Irradiation Facility Laboratory, Nuclear Department, ENEA, Roma, Italy

⁴ Department of Applied Science and Technology, Politecnico di Torino, Italy

⁵ Istituto Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare, Sezione di Torino, Italy

* Contact: valentina.pinto@enea.it

The gamma radiation hardness of High Temperature Superconductors (HTS) was extensively studied in the past focusing on polycrystalline bulk materials. However, inconsistent behaviour was often reported making the comparison among the results rather difficult. Thus, the origin of some contradictions has not been completely understood yet. The recent interest on the use of HTS in compact nuclear fusion plants has renewed the need of elucidating the gamma irradiation effects on HTS coated conductors. Some papers have been recently published, confirming conflicting results on these systems [1–5]. In the present work, we tried to clarify some critical aspects of irradiation experiments by carrying out a more systematic approach. Several commercial HTS materials, both REBa₂Cu₃O_{7-δ} (REBCO, RE=Y or rare earths) tapes and Bi_{2-x}Pb_xSr₂Ca₂Cu₃O_{10-y} wires, and lab-scale chemically deposited YBa₂Cu₃O_{7-δ} films were investigated. The irradiation test was carried out at the CALLIOPE Facility in ENEA, a pool-type irradiation plant equipped with a 60Co gamma source. All samples were sealed in dry atmosphere and irradiated at room temperature. To ensure statistical significance three replicates for each material, both commercial and lab-scale, were simultaneously exposed to gamma rays with a dose/rate equal to 3.9 kGy/h and up to a total absorbed dose of 7.1 MGy. The results obtained on commercial REBCO samples, in terms of critical temperature (T_c) and critical current (I_c) dependence on magnetic field at 77K (up to 5T), evidenced no relevant differences. On the contrary, inconsistent results were observed for the lab-scale samples, despite each of them was characterized before and after irradiation. It can be supposed that some of the observed degradation effects could be ascribed to the interaction of photons with the testing environment rather than with the HTS material. Therefore, this study underlines the absolute necessity of experiments carried out in the real operative conditions, i.e. transport measurements under cryogenic irradiation. For this purpose, the design of the proper system for *in situ* measurements during gamma irradiation in liquid nitrogen environment at fusion relevant conditions is being implemented and preliminary indications will be presented.

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Athermal defect recombination after collision cascades: comparison of metals, semiconductors and ceramics

J. K. Nordlund^{1,*}, F. Djurabekova¹, and F. Granberg¹

¹Department of Physics, University of Helsinki, Finland

* Contact: kai.nordlund@helsinki.fi

The traditional picture of radiation damage in materials being produced in the form of Frenkel pairs and possibly their clusters is practically never valid. This is because the recoil spectrum of any particle except electrons almost always contains a tail of high-energy recoils, which produce a major fraction of the damage [1]. Moreover, when these recoils are in the keV energy range, the damage is produced in dense collision cascades, heat spikes. The heat spikes behave quite differently in different classes of materials [2]. In metals, due to the efficient recrystallization, almost all damage is recombined athermally [3]. In semiconductors, much of the damage remains in the form of disordered damage pockets/amorphous zones, although there is also some degree of recrystallization [1]. In ceramic materials, which include high-temperature superconductors, the situation is the most complex: some show major recombination, while others amorphize [4, 5]. In this presentation, we will discuss the dynamics of athermal recombination of damage in cascades and what is known about its significance in metals, semiconductors and ceramic materials.

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De-risking the build and nuclear operation of HTS magnets for spherical tokamaks

S. Chislett-McDonald^{1,*}

¹ Tokamak Energy Ltd, TE Magnetics, Oxfordshire, OX14 4SD, United Kingdom

* Contact: simon.chislett-mcdonald@tokamakenergy.com

Tokamak Energy (TE) has been working on a range of technology blocks and magnet demonstrators to raise the Technical Readiness Level (TRL) of REBCO HTS based magnets for spherical tokamaks (ST). This is a broad programme addressing technologies including coil manufacturing, quench protection, modelling and simulation, HTS irradiation, and other aspects. This talk will demonstrate how our current active development programmes are derisking our journey to delivery of the HTS coil systems for fusion pilot plants, with particular focus on HTS irradiation. An overview of the irradiation studies conducted to-date by TE and its partners as well as our plans for cryogenic neutron irradiation of HTS tapes and coils, shall be presented.

REBCO tapes irradiated in a background field at cryogenic temperatures with *in situ* I_c and T_c measurements

Z. L. Fisher^{1,2,*}, D. X. Fischer², K. B. Woller², A. R. Devitre^{1,2}, A. Kaplan¹,
M. P. Short¹, Z. S. Hartwig^{1,2}

¹ Department of Nuclear Science and Engineering, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Cambridge, USA

² Plasma Science and Fusion Center, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Cambridge, USA

* Contact: zlfisher@mit.edu

The design life of magnetic fusion power plants (FPP) is set by the radiation tolerance of its superconducting magnet system. Since little to no performance degradation is allowed, the maximum dose ϕ_{\max} (neutrons/m²) is often considered to be where the critical current, I_c , drops back to its original value after an initial increase due to the addition of radiation-induced flux pinning defects. For rare earth barium copper oxide (REBCO) conductors irradiated in the core of a Triga Mark-II reactor at 350 K, $\phi_{\max} \approx 3 \times 10^{22}$ neutrons/m² when measuring I_c at 30 K and 15 T, similar to the operating conditions of fusion magnets. Using this value, the ARC conceptual design study published by Sorbom et al. in 2015 projected 9 years of full-power operations. Significant efforts have since been made to better emulate the degradation of REBCO at the operating conditions of magnets in a fusion environment. For instance, we found that irradiation at 20 K resulted in a degradation rate at least 1.6x faster than irradiation at 300 K, highlighting the crucial role of irradiation temperature on degradation. Here we present on the addition of a permanent magnet to our facility to emulate ever more closely the conditions of a fusion environment. We discuss a series of proton irradiation experiments evaluating the combined effects of a magnetic field (~ 0.3 T) *present during* cryogenic irradiation with *in situ* transport current measurements. In particular, we will consider whether the forces between pinned flux lines can alter the formation kinetics of the defect landscape, and whether the hypothesized effect will increase or decrease the lifetime of REBCO magnets under irradiation.

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Probing Disorder in Ion Irradiated REBCO Coated Conductors

J. Lewis^{1,3,*}, A. Gupta¹, J. Fihosy^{1,3}, M. Coulson¹, J. Tufnail¹, K. Adams¹, C. Barker¹, N. Peng²,
D. Gianolio³, V. Celorrio³, S. Hayama³, C. Grovenor¹, R. Nicholls¹,
S. Diaz-Moreno³, and S. Speller¹

¹ Centre for Applied Superconductivity, Materials Department, University of Oxford, Oxford, UK

² Surrey Ion Beam Centre, University of Surrey, Guildford, UK

³ Spectroscopy Group, Diamond Light Source, Harwell Science Campus, UK

* Contact: jarrod.lewis@materials.ox.ac.uk

For rare-earth barium cuprate (REBCO) components in compact spherical tokamaks, it is well established that the incident flux of neutrons will affect the superconducting properties of the material without sufficient shielding [1,2], potentially limiting the operational component lifetime. Although this raises questions about reactor design and shielding material choices [3,4], the mechanisms through which irradiation degrades the performance of REBCO remain uncertain. To this end, we present the results of a long running X-ray characterisation study of commercially sourced REBCO coated conductors provided by various manufacturers, where both synchrotron and laboratory X-ray techniques are used to synergistically probe the evolution of the material in response to bombardment with accelerated He⁺ ions. Here, ions are used as proxies for the energetic neutrons anticipated within the fusion environment, based on previous work that observed a similarity in the point defects induced in REBCO when comparing He⁺ ions and fission spectrum neutrons [5]. 2 MeV irradiation treatments are chosen to provide a homogeneous damage profile throughout the REBCO layer of the coated conductor based on SRIM simulations.

Here the static structure of the REBCO unit cell is probed using laboratory Cu K α X-ray diffraction (XRD), characterising the unit cell dimensions and the relative broadening of Bragg reflections with specular and off-specular diffraction and rocking curves. Relative trends in lattice expansion and peak broadening will be discussed as a function of irradiation displacements-per-atom (dpa), and will inform subsequent analysis of synchrotron data. To probe for irradiation induced defects within the REBCO unit cell, X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS) data will be discussed, with a particular focus on analysis of the extended X-ray absorption fine-structure (EXAFS). This local structure probe ($\approx 6 \text{ \AA}$) allows stacking faults in the pristine material to be identified, and for shifts in atomic site positions to be observed as a function of dpa using a volume averaged measurement. Furthermore, high-energy resolution fluorescence detected X-ray absorption near-edge structure (HERFD-XANES) spectra will be presented, highlighting the subtle variation in the local environment of Cu atoms within the REBCO unit cell in response to these irradiations.

Together, these techniques allow the evolution of the REBCO matrix in response to ion bombardment to be explored, building on our previous studies in which we exploit the polarisation of synchrotron X-rays to probe variations in the structurally anisotropic REBCO unit cell [6,7]. With these experiments, we aim to link our induced dpa to observables within the material structure, providing further context for irradiation performance studies within the field.

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Atomistic simulations of exceptional radiation stability of gallium oxide crystals

F. Djurabekova^{1,*}, R. He¹, Ch. Nozais¹, J. Zhao²

¹Department of Physics, University of Helsinki, Helsinki, Finland

²Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering, Southern University of Science and Technology, Shenzhen, China

* Contact: flyura.djurabekova@helsinki.fi

In our group, we study the radiation resistance of materials, exposed to extensive ion or neutron irradiation. Conventionally, metals and many oxides show strong resistance to irradiation, while semiconductor materials exposed to long ion irradiation become amorphous after a threshold dose has been reached. This indicates that the damage of such a material proceeds gradually, accumulating defects in subsequent cascades without exhibiting any self-healing tendencies. Recently, gallium oxide, one of the wide-band semiconductors, has drawn much attention of the scientists in different fields because of its surprisingly high radiation resistance [1]. The amorphization threshold for this material has been shifted to two orders of magnitude higher levels of dpa, see Fig.1. However, the mechanisms behind this exceptional stability remain unclear. Our atomistic simulations, utilizing machine-learning interatomic potentials, in a very good agreement with experimental images of irradiated samples reveal the important role of oxygen sublattice that shows strong recovery tendency upon irradiation. The sublattice maintains its FCC packing in several Ga₂O₃ polymorphs, which suggests a possible crystal-to-crystal phase transition under irradiation. In our recent work we show indeed that such phase transition is possible [2].

However, RBS/C analysis of irradiated structures indicates a high level of disorder in β -Ga₂O₃ before its transition to the γ phase. In our study, we model the damage accumulation in β -Ga₂O₃ cells and simulate the RBS/C signal from these structures to compare with experimental data. We explore possible reasons for high RBS/C signals by considering various scenarios of phase transition between the two polymorphs. Moreover, we examine the dynamic response of the β -Ga₂O₃ structure to ion irradiation with up to 150 MeV. At these high energies, the interaction with atomic nuclei becomes insignificant and the energy loss in the material proceeds via the interaction with electrons. In collaboration with the experimentalists, we show the intriguing observation of no damage in defective γ -Ga₂O₃ polymorph.

Our results indicate the important role of strain effects in the crystal-to-crystal transition between polymorphs, which may not be present in low energy regime. The mechanisms identified for gallium oxide material, its surprising tendency for self-recovery can indicate the existence of similar mechanism in materials with similar structural properties.

Figure 1: Comparison of threshold dose for amorphization in different semiconductor materials.[1]

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Pinning variabilities in REBCO coated conductors and its potential vulnerabilities under irradiation

F. Kametani^{1,2,*}, A. Xu¹, Y. Xin², C. Watson¹, J. Lee¹, J. Bang¹,
J. Jaroszynski², D. Abraimov¹, D. Larbalestier^{1,3,4}

¹ Applied Superconductivity Center, National High Magnetic Field Laboratory, Florida State University, FL, USA

² National High Magnetic Field Laboratory, Florida State University, FL, USA

³ Department of Mechanical Engineering, FAMU-FSU College of Engineering, Florida State University, FL, USA

⁴ Department of Materials Science & Engineering, FAMU-FSU College of Engineering, Florida State University, FL, USA

* Contact: kametani@asc.magnet.fsu.edu

High critical current density J_c of REBCO coated conductors (CCs) has been achieved by a complex pinning design, but this can only be done by developing highly engineered nanostructures that may not be easy to control in quantity production of long length and are significant variable among the manufacturers. Indeed, controlling $J_c(\theta, B, T)$ and pinning structure is technical challenge for the manufacturers, and correlations between $J_c(\theta, B, T)$ and pinning structure becomes more complicated in the low temperature and high field regimes like the targeted operation at 20 K, 20 T in the recent HTS Fusion Tokamak designs. At high temperature such as 77 K, the dominant pinning mechanism in the modern REBCO CCs is artificial pinning centers (so-called strong pin) of 2nd phase nanorods and nanoparticles whose shape, size and density determines $J_c(\theta, B)$. However, at the low temperature and high field regimes, the weak pins such as oxygen vacancies which are a by-product of the strongly strained interfaces of strong pins become dominant in determining $J_c(\theta, B, T)$, making the assessment and understanding of pinning more complicated. Comparing the spool or production batches of CC tape delivered to MagLab, we found that I_c (77 K, s.f) shows consistency (~25% variation) among the delivered tapes, but I_c (4.2 K, 17 T, 18° from the ab-plane) shows ~250% variation [1]. Even though the manufacturer targeted to make it consistent and optimum (~6 nm in diameter), Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) analysis revealed the large Ba-ZrO₃ size and density variation, presumably causing large variation in the density of point pins created by the strained BZO-REBCO interfaces. Interestingly, the nanostructure of strong pins has become less dependent on the nanorod precipitates in more recent PLD REBCO conductors, creating ~300 % variation of J_c at B//c-axis and 77 K, but such large variation at B//c-axis disappear at 20 K in high fields, leaving 50-100 % J_c variation at B//ab-plane [2], presumably due to the variability of weak pins between the conductors. One of the important questions to the fusion community is how the structure of strong pins and weak pins can be modulated or altered by neutron irradiation, because we don't fully understand how the cascade scattering caused by high energy neutron flux interacts with the nanorod or nano particle precipitates themselves and/or their interfaces whose degradation may strongly vary among the conductors. In this presentation, we will overview the variation of pinning nanostructures in modern REBCO CCs and the methodologies of $J_c(\theta, B, T)$ assessment, and discuss the possibility that some of them fall from the envelop of specification requirements for HTS Fusion magnet use if the pinning nanostructures, interfaces and/or the density of weak pins are strongly degraded under the high energy neutron irradiation in the fusion applications.

Acknowledgments

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A ladder approach to investigate radiation damage in coated conductors for magnetic confinement fusion reactors magnets

L. Civale^{1,*}, A. R. Devitre², Z. L. Fisher², B. Maiorov³, S. M. Bergeron Hartman³, J. Pfund¹,
M. Jain¹, B. Clark², D. X. Fischer², B. Sarangi⁴, M. Paulose⁴ and V. Selvamanickam⁴

¹ University of Connecticut, Storrs, CT, USA

² Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Cambridge, MA, USA

³ Los Alamos National Laboratory, Los Alamos, NM, USA

⁴ University of Houston, Houston, TX, USA

* Contact: lcivale@outlook.com

To determine the operational lifetime of the coated conductor (CC) magnets for compact fusion reactors, it is necessary to know the effects of radiation damage on the critical current density J_c of the superconducting tapes. The initial J_c of the CC is determined by the vortex pinning generated by various types of defects, both spontaneously occurring and introduced as artificial pinning centers (APC), which act in combination, producing cooperative and competitive effects. These complex pinning landscapes result in J_c dependencies with temperature (T) and magnetic field intensity (B) and orientation (Θ) that are unique to each deposition method, to the APC nanoengineering, and to processing parameters.

Radiation will create defects that will act as additional pinning centers and may initially increase J_c , but will also reduce the superfluid density, thus it will always decrease J_c below acceptable values at high enough doses. The effects of the radiation will depend on the preexisting pinning landscape, thus the evolution of $J_c(B, \Theta, T)$ with dose must be investigated for each CC and for each reactor design. According to plans, fusion magnets will operate between 4.2 and 30 K in fields up to 20 T, implying that J_c must be determined up to $B > 20$ T, for $T \geq 4.2$ K, and for all Θ . These extensive studies can only be performed in a limited number of facilities, and a complete characterization will be time-consuming and expensive. Although that detailed investigation cannot be totally avoided, we have designed an approach to make that process as efficient as possible.

The basic idea is that CCs have several pinning regimes in the B - Θ - T space that can be identified by the functional dependence of $J_c(B, \Theta, T)$. It is extremely difficult (if not impossible) to infer the effects that adding defects will have in one regime by measuring their effects in another one. However, if the functional dependencies of $J_c(B, \Theta, T)$ are known, we can apply scaling rules to infer J_c at different B - Θ - T conditions *as long as the sample remains in the same pinning regime*. Our approach is to map the dependences and boundaries of those regimes in the B - Θ - T space for unirradiated CCs, identify which are relevant to fusion reactor magnets, and then follow their evolution with fluence for different types of irradiations (neutron, proton) at various conditions (room or cryogenic temperature) and after thermal annealing, using a “ladder of experiments” of increasing complexity, from permanent magnets to electromagnets, SQUID up to 7 T and VSM up to 14 T, and pulsed fields up to 65 T; each step informing the next one. Thus, the irradiation effects can be assessed by performing extensive studies using fast and easily accessible systems, complemented with a limited number of the more involved measurements at selected samples and conditions. In this talk I will describe our methodology and present initial results for unirradiated and irradiated samples.

Sponsor Unico Industriale**ENI COMPANY PROFILE**

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Eni corporate contacts:

Press office: +39 0252031875 – +39 0659822030

Shareholders' toll-free number (from Italy): +800 94 09 24

Shareholders' toll-free number (from abroad): +800 11 22 34 56

Switchboard: +39 0659821

ufficio.stampa@eni.com

segreteria.societaria.azionisti@eni.com

investor.relations@eni.com

Website: www.eni.com